

Supplementary figure S2: Cleaned phasing results for all 35 strains

We present the three plots generated for each strain's cleaned nPhase phasing predictions, generated from the raw predictions. For each strain, the first plot shows the coverage of each predicted haplotig, the second plot shows the discordance level of each predicted haplotig, and the final plot shows an overview of where the haplotigs are along the genome.

AFP - Coverage

AFP - Discordance

AFP - Phased

ANL - Coverage

ANL - Discordance

ANL - Phased

AQH - Coverage

AQH - Discordance

AQH - Phased

AQT - Coverage

AQT - Discordance

AQT - Phased

ARE - Coverage

ARE - Discordance

ARE - Phased

ASB - Coverage

ASB - Discordance

ASB - Phased

ASC - Coverage

ASC - Discordance

ASC - Phased

ASD - Coverage

ASD - Discordance

ASD - Phased

AVN - Coverage

AVN - Discordance

AVN - Phased

AVQ - Coverage

AVQ - Discordance

AVQ - Phased

AVS - Coverage

AVS - Discordance

AVS - Phased

AVT - Phased

BBG - Coverage

BBG - Discordance

BBG - Phased

BDL - Coverage

BDL - Discordance

BDL - Phased

BEM - Coverage

BEM - Discordance

BEM - Phased

BHA - Coverage

BHA - Discordance

BHA - Phased

BRP - Coverage

BRP - Discordance

BRP - Phased

BSI - Coverage

BSI - Discordance

BSI - Phased

CFC - Coverage

CFC - Discordance

CFC - Phased

CFE - Coverage

CFE - Discordance

CFE - Phased

CFF - Coverage

CFF - Discordance

CFF - Phased

CFG - Coverage

CFG - Discordance

CFG - Phased

CFH - Coverage

CFH - Discordance

CFH - Phased

CFM - Coverage

CFM - Discordance

CFM - Phased

CFN - Coverage

CFN - Discordance

CFN - Phased

CFP - Coverage

CFP - Discordance

CFP - Phased

CGC - Coverage

CGC - Discordance

CGC - Phased

CPB - Coverage

CPB - Discordance

CPB - Phased

YMD1864 - Coverage

YMD1864 - Discordance

YMD1864 - Phased

YMD1870 - Coverage

YMD1870 - Discordance

YMD1870 - Phased

YMD1871 - Coverage

YMD1871 - Discordance

YMD1871 - Phased

YMD1873 - Coverage

YMD1873 - Discordance

YMD1873 - Phased

YMD1950 - Coverage

YMD1950 - Discordance

YMD1950 - Phased

YMD1981 - Coverage

YMD1981 - Discordance

YMD1981 - Phased

YMD4285 - Coverage

YMD4285 - Discordance

YMD4285 - Phased

